

Maxwell-Boltzmann Gas Pressure Ideas Applied to a Single Particle Yields $\exp(ipx)$?

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A Maxwell-Boltzmann gas with no external potential $V(x)$ has a constant spatial density. The value of this spatial density alone does not yield the pressure because this also depends on T through the ideal gas law $\text{Pressure} = \text{density}(x) RT$, where T is temperature (associated with a conserved average energy), but also the average single particle pressure. Taking $d/\text{density}(x)$ of Pressure yields the single particle average pressure value RT , yet at the same time single particle pressure is a stochastic value evaluated as the average of constant $v p$ where p is momentum and v velocity. The quadratic form of p arises, we argue, because one has more than one particle, thus v distinguishes between the particles and relative speed becomes important.

In the case of a single particle (as in a single free quantum particle) moving at constant p (speed as well) there is again a constant spatial density as in the MB gas with no $V(x)$. Given the value of the constant density $1/L$ ($L=\text{length}$), one has no information about momentum p . In the case of a single particle, impulse and not pressure is the important quantity, we argue, because there is no need for a v as there is no relative motion. One only needs to know impulse which is proportional to p . If one speculates that a free quantum particle may follow the model of pressure in an MB gas, one would require a function $F(p,x)$ such that $d/d \text{something} F = p$ where p is the single particle impulse. In the MB case, "something" is density, but this is not appropriate for a single particle as density consists of many particles. Without changing T , one may change pressure in an MB gas by changing density i.e. changing the x value of particles. For a quantum particle, we suggest that the conjugate variable to p is x . One may change x of the single particle. Furthermore an association between d/dx and p exists in Fermat's Least Time Principle. T

Thus we suggest $d/dx F(p,x) = p$ where F is unknown both in form and meaning. Pressure, however, is a statistical quantity so F should also be a statistical quantity i.e. one could have $d/dx P(p,x) / P(p,x) = \text{constant } p$ where $P(p,x)$ is a kind of unnormalized probability. This suggests, however, that $P(p,x)$ is an eigenfunction of d/dx and represents a kind of unnormalized probability. This, we argue, leads to the notion of $\exp(ipx)$ because one does not want a monotonically growing or decreasing probability in x for a constant p . The "constant" is then i . Thus, we argue that if one mimics the pressure behaviour of a MB gas, and applies its properties to a single particle moving at constant speed, one obtains an unusual unnormalized kind of probability $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. the quantum free particle wavefunction. At the same time, a constant spatial probability or density $1/L$ exists. The two are linked in that $\exp(ipx) \exp(-ipx) = 1$.

The overall idea is that the stochastic force i.e. the entropic pressure in an MB gas has an analogy even for a single particle with constant momentum.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Gas, Spatial Density and Pressure

An MB gas with no potential $V(x)$ has a constant spatial density. This density does not reveal information about the pressure or temperature of the gas. Rather it represents the number of particles in a volume. At the same there exists stochastic behaviour, i.e. $P(e/T)$, which is

associated with a conserved quantity, average energy proportional to T , and T (or RT) itself represents the average pressure of a single particle. Thus pressure overall satisfies the ideal gas law:

$$\text{Pressure} = \text{density}(x) RT \quad ((1))$$

At the same time pressure is a stochastic quantity given by the average of constant p v i.e.

$$\text{Pressure} = \text{Number of particles} \int dv pv \text{ constant } \exp(-pv/2mT) / \{ \int dv \exp(-pv/2mT) \} \quad ((2)) \quad (\text{one dimension})$$

If one examines the expression $p \cdot v$, p is proportional to impulse, and v to flux. If one has a single particle one might wonder why v would be necessary. If $p = m_1 v_1 = m_2 v_2$ and $v_2 > v_1$, the second particle reaches a target first, but renders the same impulse hit as v_1 . The time taken to reach the target does not seem to be a relevant piece of information. If many particles are present, however, there are a certain number of particles hitting a target in a certain time i.e. a steady stream picture. Thus the idea of pressure is needed.

If one examines ((1)):

$$d/d \text{ density}(x) \text{ Pressure} = RT \quad \text{which is the average pressure of a single particle} \quad ((3))$$

It is also associated with a constant quantity in the system T which in turn is associated with conserved average energy. On the other, ((2)) shows that pressure is a stochastic quantity. Thus there are two key ideas {((2)) and ((3))} associated with pressure, we argue.

Quantum Free Particle

Classically a free particle with constant speed and momentum moves such that $x = vt + x_0$. One may consider the notion of a density(x), like in the MB case with no $V(x)$, and it is a constant which gives no information about p (momentum) just as the MB case gives no information about T . In the MB case, RT is the average pressure for a single particle. In the single particle case, p is proportional to the impulse of the single particle. We have argued above that impulse i.e. p is appropriate for a single particle, while pressure is necessary for many particles.

Thus one may try to apply the ideas ((3)) and ((2)) to a single particle impulse i.e. momentum p .

First of all, there is no adjustable density for a single particle if p is constant. One does not have many particles which may be shifted in space i.e. x as in the MB gas case. One may, however, shift the one particle in x i.e. change its x value. This suggests that d/dx may take the place of $d/d \text{ density}(x)$ in ((3)). We argue that this idea is strengthened by Fermat's Least Time Principle for Light.

Fermat's principle, which is often applied to reflection and refraction problems, deals with the least time for light to travel from a starting point, reflect or refract at some x point on a flat surface along the x axis and reach a final point. Light travels at a constant speed given by c/n , where n is the index of refraction. Thus time may be replaced with: $x/(c/n)$. Fermat's Least Time principle then really deals with changing paths in space. This is linked to d/dx and

$p(x)$ being constant. Fermat's principle seems to suggest that constant $p(x)$ and d/dx are linked, with d/dx acting on some function of x .

As a result, we consider ((3)) for an MB gas, but replace pressure with p and d/d density(x) with d/dx . As a result, there should exist a function $F(x,p)$ such that;

$$d/dx F(p,x) = p = \text{average impulse of a single particle} \quad ((4))$$

At present, $F(p,x)$ is completely unknown, both in terms of its mathematical form and its physical meaning.

((2)) from the MB gas, however, suggests that pressure is a stochastic function. Thus, d/dx in ((4)) should operate on an unnormalized probability with probability in the denominator as a normalization i.e.

$$d/dx P(p,x) / P(p,x = \text{constant } p) \quad ((5))$$

Here $P(p,x)$ is now a kind of probability linked to both p (momentum) and x . Thus there are now two probabilities in the problem: $P(x)=\text{constant}$ and $P(p,x)$ which is an eigenfunction of d/dx with an eigenvalue of p constant (where the modulus of the constant should be 1). This leads to the solution:

$$P(p,x) = \exp(ipx) = \text{unnormalized kind of probability and constant} = i \quad ((6))$$

As a result, mimicking the behaviour of MB gas pressure ((3)) and ((2)), with single particle adjustments, yields a stochastic picture for a single particle moving with constant p i.e. kind of unnormalized probability of $\exp(ipx)$ which is the quantum free particle wavefunction.

In other words, both the MB gas "force" and the free particle impulse are statistical and follow a similar force-based scenario.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we first note that a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas has a constant spatial density if there is no potential $V(x)$ present which does not reveal information about T , temperature which is also proportional to single particle average pressure. Next, we consider the behaviour of pressure which is a stochastic force. The ideal gas law applies so: Pressure = density(x) RT . This suggests that RT (a constant) is the average pressure of a single particle. Thus: $d\text{Pressure}/d \text{density}(x) = RT = \text{average single particle pressure}$. Secondly. Pressure may be obtained from the average:

$$\text{Pressure} = \text{constant} \{ \text{Integral } dv \, pv \exp(-pp/2mT) \} / \{ \text{Integral } dv \exp(-pp/2mT) \}$$

In this note, we suggest applying these two ideas related to pressure in an MB gas to a single particle moving at a constant speed i.e with a constant momentum p . We note that like in the MB case, the spatial density or probability is a constant and gives no information about p , the impulse rendered by the single particle. Next, we note that for a single particle, p which is

proportional to impulse replaces pressure because there is no relative motion of particles. "pv" is needed in the pressure expression because there are many particles moving at relative speeds so one considers impulse per time with the "time" value in the impulse ($\int dt \text{ Force}$) canceling the time in the per time from the flux. For a single particle, one is only interested in the impulse rendered by it, not at what time this occurs. Thus $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ with $v_2>v_1$, yield the same impulse albeit at different times.

Next, we note that there is no density of particles for a single particle. $d/d \text{ density}(x)$ Pressure, however, involves changing the x position of particles in a gas. Thus we argue that for a single particle changing x is the relevant variable, replacing density(x) in the MB case. We further argue that this idea is supported by Fermat's Least Time principle for light as argued above. As a result, $d/d \text{ density Pressure} = RT = \text{average pressure}$ for a single particle is replaced with: $p = \text{impulse} = d/dx F(p,x)$. $F(p,x)$, however, is unknown both in math form and meaning.

The second MB pressure condition, however, shows that single particle pressure is an average quantity. Thus $d/dx F(p,x)$ is like $p P(p,x)/P(p,x)$ where $P(p,x)$ is a kind of probability. In other words: $d/dx P(p,x) = p \text{ constant } P(p,x)$ where the constant has modulus 1. In order to not have $P(p,x)$ grow or decrease monotonically in x, we use $P(p,x) = \exp(ipx) = \text{unnormalized probability}$. There are now two probabilities in the picture, $P(x) = \text{constant}$ and $\exp(ipx)$, but $\exp(ipx)\exp(-pix) = 1$ so there is a link between the two. $\exp(ipx)$ is the quantum free particle wavefunction.

Thus we argue that using the Maxwell-Boltzmann model applied to a stochastic pressure and modifying it for a single particle by associating pressure with p and $d/d \text{ density}(x)$ with d/dx and utilizing stochastic behaviour leading to the "force" (pressure or impulse of a single particle) yields the quantum mechanical $\exp(ipx)$.